

Politically Induced Economic Hardship and Suicidal Tendencies in Nigeria

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Abstract

The confluence of economic hardship and its adverse impact on the mental health of youths, particularly concerning suicide tendencies, has emerged as a pressing concern in contemporary society. As economies face challenges ranging from financial crises to persistent unemployment, young individuals often find themselves disproportionately affected by economic instability. This essay explores how political-instigated economic hardship has increased suicide tendencies in Nigeria. The present article calls for the government to ensure that mental health services are readily available and easily accessible to those experiencing economic hardship. This can include hotlines, online counselling services, support groups, and subsidised therapy sessions. Governments and organisations should allocate resources to bolster mental health infrastructure and reduce barriers to access. More so, there is a need to foster strong community support networks to provide emotional, practical, and financial assistance to those in need. Local organisations, religious institutions, and volunteer groups can play a crucial role in offering solidarity, empathy, and tangible support to individuals grappling with economic hardships. Community-based initiatives can also help combat social isolation and provide a sense of belonging.

Keywords: Economic hardship, Mental health, Politics, Social isolation, Suicide tendencies.

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376

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the intersection between economic hardship and its profound impact on the mental health of youths, particularly in relation to suicide tendencies, has garnered increasing attention from researchers, policymakers, and public health advocates. Economic instability, characterized by high rates of unemployment, underemployment, and financial insecurity, has emerged as a significant stressor for many young individuals, exacerbating their vulnerability to mental health challenges, including suicidal ideation and behavior. The global economic landscape has witnessed tumultuous shifts, marked by financial crises, widening income inequality, and the proliferation of precarious employment opportunities, all of which have disproportionately affected the younger demographic. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), suicide ranks as the second leading cause of death among individuals aged 15 to 29 years, underscoring the urgent need to understand and address the underlying socio-economic factors contributing to this alarming trend (WHO, 2014).

Although suicide is under-reported and misclassified more frequently than most other causes of death, it is estimated that around 800,000 individuals take their own lives each year, with many more attempting suicide (Van Harmelen et al., 2019; WHO, 2021). For instance, the United States (US) witnessed over 47,500 deaths due to suicide in 2019, and the suicide rate escalated by 33% between 1999 and 2019 (Abdou et al., 2022). This highlights the crucial need to understand the underlying motivators and factors contributing to suicide to devise efficacious preventive interventions and enhance public awareness

The confluence of economic hardship and its adverse impact on the mental health of youths, particularly concerning suicide tendencies, has emerged as a pressing concern in contemporary society. As economies face challenges ranging from financial crises to persistent unemployment, young individuals often find themselves disproportionately affected by economic instability. This essay explores the complex relationship between economic adversity and suicide among youths, drawing upon empirical evidence and theoretical frameworks to elucidate key determinants and implications.

Economic hardship encompasses a range of stressors, including unemployment, poverty, financial strain, and housing instability, all of which can profoundly affect the mental well-being of young individuals. The experience of economic deprivation during formative years can contribute to feelings of hopelessness, despair, and anxiety, thereby increasing the risk of suicidal ideation and behavior (Liu & Miller, 2014). Studies have consistently demonstrated a positive association between economic adversity and youth mental health problems, with economic downturns often exacerbating pre-existing vulnerabilities (Chang et al., 2020).

Several pathways elucidate the link between economic hardship and suicide tendencies among youths. Firstly, financial strain can contribute to heightened psychological distress, leading to conditions such as depression and anxiety, which are known risk factors for suicidal behavior (Platt et al., 2016). Secondly, economic instability can disrupt social support networks, exacerbating feelings of isolation and loneliness, which further increase the risk of suicide (Fitzpatrick et al., 2019). Thirdly, disparities in access to mental health services often leave economically marginalized youths underserved, hindering their ability to seek help and support (Stack, 2018).

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378

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The impact of economic hardship on suicide tendencies among youths is not uniform and often intersects with existing socioeconomic disparities. Marginalized groups, including racial and ethnic minorities, LGBTQ+ individuals, and those with disabilities, may face heightened vulnerabilities due to intersecting forms of discrimination and disadvantage (Haas et al., 2010). Addressing these disparities requires a multifaceted approach that acknowledges the intersecting influences of socioeconomic status, identity, and structural inequalities. Efforts to address economic hardship and suicide tendencies among youths necessitate a comprehensive, multi-sectoral approach. Policy interventions aimed at reducing economic inequality, promoting youth employment, and enhancing access to mental health services are crucial steps in mitigating the risk factors associated with suicidal behavior (Gunnell et al., 2014). Additionally, community-based initiatives that foster social connectedness, resilience, and coping skills can help buffer the adverse effects of economic adversity on youth mental health (Wyman et al., 2010).

Economic hardship represents a significant risk factor for suicide tendencies among youths, exerting a profound impact on their mental well-being and overall health outcomes. Addressing this complex issue requires a concerted effort from policymakers, healthcare providers, educators, and community stakeholders. By implementing evidence-based interventions that prioritize mental health promotion, economic equity, and social support, we can work towards creating a more resilient and inclusive society where all young individuals have the opportunity to thrive.

Undoubtedly, trends and patterns of suicidal behaviour are important in having a clear understanding of the size of the problem, its distribution in the population and the major risk and

protective factors at individual and community levels. This necessitated how political instigated economic hardship has increased suicide tendencies in Nigeria.

2. A conceptual view of suicide

Suicide is the act of intentionally taking one's own life (Gvion & Apter, 2012). It is a complex and tragic event that can have profound emotional, psychological, and social impacts on individuals, families, and communities. Suicide is often regarded as a result of deep psychological pain, despair, hopelessness, or extreme distress that an individual may experience. It's critical to understand that suicide is not simply a result of personal weakness or a lack of moral character, but rather a manifestation of severe mental health challenges and other underlying factors. It's important to recognise that suicidal behaviour exists on a spectrum, ranging from suicidal ideation (thoughts of suicide) to suicide attempts and completed suicide (Barraclough et al., 1975). Not everyone who experiences suicidal thoughts will act on them, and there are opportunities for intervention and support at each stage of the suicidal process.

Suicide is a final act of behavior, likely resulting from the interaction of several different factors. It is a complex entity, involving biological, genetic, and environmental risk factors. Sociopolitical factors are also pertinent to the understanding of suicide. Thus, Durkheim, in his historical treatise on suicide, coined the terms anomy, egoistic, and altruistic. These ideas are still inferred today. Predictors of suicidal behaviour and risk factors include a history of previous suicide attempts, certain demographic variables, clinical symptoms, and issues related to medical and social support (Beck et al., 1985).

Suicide is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon influenced by a combination of biological, psychological, social, and environmental factors. Here's an explanation:

1. **Mental health factors:** Mental health conditions, particularly mood disorders like depression and bipolar disorder, are significant risk factors for suicide. Individuals experiencing intense psychological pain or hopelessness may consider suicide as a way to escape their suffering.
2. **Biological Factors:** There's evidence suggesting that genetic, neurological, and biochemical factors may contribute to an individual's vulnerability to suicidal thoughts and behaviors. For instance, alterations in serotonin levels in the brain have been linked to impulsivity and suicidal behaviour.
3. **Psychological Factors:** Certain psychological traits, such as impulsivity, aggression, and a history of trauma or abuse, can increase the likelihood of suicidal behavior. Additionally, feelings of loneliness, social isolation, and perceived burdensomeness may exacerbate suicidal ideation.
4. **Social and Environmental Factors:** Social determinants, including adverse life events, exposure to violence or trauma, relationship conflicts, financial difficulties, and access to lethal means, can significantly influence suicide risk. Social support networks and access to mental health care services play crucial roles in mitigating these risk factors.
5. **Cultural and Societal Factors:** Cultural attitudes, norms, and beliefs surrounding mental health and suicide can shape individuals' perceptions and help-seeking behaviors. Stigmatisation, discrimination, and a lack of awareness about mental health issues may deter individuals from seeking help and exacerbate feelings of shame or guilt.

Preventing suicide requires a comprehensive approach that addresses both individual risk factors and broader societal determinants. This includes promoting mental health awareness and literacy, reducing stigma associated with seeking help, improving access to mental health care services, implementing policies to restrict access to lethal means, fostering supportive communities and social networks, and enhancing crisis intervention and suicide prevention strategies.

3. Examining the various types of suicide

Suicide is a complex phenomenon with various contributing factors. While there are many ways to categorize suicide, one common classification is based on the motives or underlying reasons behind the act. Sociologist Emile Durkheim proposed several types of suicide in his seminal work, "Suicide: A Study in Sociology" (1897). According to Durkheim, there are four main types of suicide, each associated with different social conditions and levels of integration within society. These types are:

1. **Egoistic suicide:** Egoistic suicide occurs when people feel disconnected or alienated from society. This type of suicide is frequently caused by a lack of social integration or weak social **bonds**. Individuals who experience egoistic suicide may feel isolated, lonely, or lacking in social support. Durkheim suggested that certain groups, such as unmarried individuals or those without strong family or community ties, may be more vulnerable to egoistic suicide. Durkheim, E., published *Suicide: A Study in Sociology* in 1897.
2. **Altruistic Suicide:** Altruistic suicide occurs when individuals feel excessively integrated into society, to the point where their personal identity becomes subsumed by group norms

or values. This type of suicide is often associated with highly cohesive or tightly knit social groups, such as military units, religious sects, or cults. Individuals who commit altruistic suicide may sacrifice their lives for the group's welfare or ideals, viewing death as a noble or honorable act. According to Durkheim, E., *Suicide: A Study in Sociology*, 1897, altruistic suicide occurs when individuals sacrifice their lives for the welfare or ideals of the group, viewing death as a noble or honourable act.

3. **Anomic Suicide:** Anomic suicide occurs during periods of social upheaval, disruption, or rapid change. It is characterised by a breakdown in social norms, values, or regulations, leading to feelings of confusion, disorientation, or moral uncertainty. Anomie refers to a state of normlessness or norm confusion, where individuals experience a lack of clarity or guidance regarding acceptable behavior. Economic crises, natural disasters, or significant life events can trigger anomic suicide by destabilising social structures and undermining individuals' sense of purpose or meaning. In 1897, Durkheim, E., published *Suicide: A Study in Sociology*.
4. **Fatalistic Suicide:** Fatalistic suicide occurs when individuals feel excessively regulated or constrained by oppressive social conditions. This type of suicide is associated with extreme control situations, such as slavery, imprisonment, or totalitarian regimes, where individuals perceive no hope of escape or improvement. Fatalistic suicide may arise from feelings of despair, powerlessness, or a desire to escape intolerable circumstances. [Durkheim, E., *Suicide: A Study in Sociology*, 1897]

5. Exploring the various levels of suicide

When discussing "levels" of suicide, it's important to clarify what aspect of suicide you are referring to. Suicide can be examined from various perspectives, including epidemiological, psychological, sociological, and public health. Here are a few ways suicide can be considered in terms of levels:

1. **Individual Level:** At the individual level, suicide refers to the act of a single person taking their own life. This can involve various factors such as mental health issues, personal struggles, traumatic experiences, or existential crises.
2. **Community Level:** Suicide can also be examined at the community or local level, considering factors such as suicide rates within a specific geographic area, community attitudes towards suicide and mental health, access to mental health services, and the presence of social support networks.
3. **National Level:** Suicide rates and trends can be analyzed at the national level, comparing rates between different countries, regions, or demographic groups. This can involve examining factors such as cultural attitudes towards suicide, socioeconomic conditions, healthcare infrastructure, and public policies related to mental health and suicide prevention.
4. **Global Level:** Suicide can be considered from a global perspective, looking at worldwide trends, disparities, and efforts to address suicide prevention on an international scale. Organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) provide data and resources for understanding global suicide rates and implementing suicide prevention strategies.

5. **Public Health Level:** Suicide is also addressed as a public health issue, involving efforts to understand risk factors, protective factors, and interventions aimed at reducing suicide rates and promoting mental well-being. This includes strategies such as suicide prevention hotlines, mental health education programs, screening and treatment for mental health disorders, and community-based suicide prevention initiatives.

Understanding suicide across these different levels requires interdisciplinary collaboration and a comprehensive approach that addresses individual, social, cultural, economic, and environmental factors. By examining suicide from multiple perspectives, researchers, policymakers, and practitioners can develop more effective strategies for suicide prevention and intervention.

6. **The various ways of managing suicide**

Managing suicide is a complex thing. However, it's important to approach it from a comprehensive perspective that includes prevention, intervention, and postvention strategies. Below are some key components of suicide management, supported by citations where available:

Suicide Prevention Programs: Suicide prevention programs aim to reduce the risk of suicidal behavior through education, awareness, and intervention. These programs often target at-risk populations, provide mental health education, and promote help-seeking behaviors (Mann, J. J., et al. (2005).

Access to Mental Health Services: Ensuring access to mental health services is crucial for individuals at risk of suicide. This includes timely access to counseling, therapy, psychiatric care, and crisis intervention services (Reger, et al., 2020).

Risk Assessment and Management: Conducting thorough risk assessments is essential for identifying individuals at risk of suicide and developing appropriate management plans. This involves assessing factors such as suicidal ideation, intent, means, and access to support systems (Stanley et al., 2013).

Crisis Intervention and Hotlines: Crisis intervention services and suicide hotlines provide immediate support and assistance to individuals experiencing a suicidal crisis. Trained counselors or volunteers offer empathetic listening, emotional support, and referrals to appropriate resources (Gould et al., 2007).

Postvention and Support for Survivors: Postvention efforts focus on providing support and assistance to individuals who have been affected by suicide, including bereaved family members, friends, and communities. This may involve grief counseling, support groups, and community-based initiatives to reduce stigma and promote healing (Cerel, et al., 2026).

Public Policy and Advocacy: Public policies play a crucial role in suicide prevention by addressing factors such as access to lethal means, mental health parity, funding for suicide prevention programs, and reducing stigma surrounding mental illness and help-seeking (Pirkis, & Mok, 2015).

These citations provide evidence and support for various strategies and approaches in managing suicide. It's important to emphasize that suicide management requires a multi-faceted and collaborative effort involving healthcare professionals, policymakers, community organizations, and individuals themselves.

7. Conclusion and recommendations

In recent years, the intersection between economic hardship and its profound impact on the mental health of youths, particularly in relation to suicide tendencies, has garnered increasing attention from researchers, policymakers, and public health advocates. Economic instability, characterized by high rates of unemployment, underemployment, and financial insecurity, has emerged as a significant stressor for many young individuals, exacerbating their vulnerability to mental health challenges, including suicidal ideation and behavior. The global economic landscape has witnessed tumultuous shifts, marked by financial crises, widening income inequality, and the proliferation of precarious employment opportunities, all of which have disproportionately affected the younger demographic. It is on this note that the present article calls for the government to ensure that mental health services are readily available and easily accessible to those experiencing economic hardship. This can include hotlines, online counseling services, support groups, and subsidized therapy sessions. Governments and organizations should allocate resources to bolster mental health infrastructure and reduce barriers to access. More so, there is need to foster strong community support networks to provide emotional, practical, and financial assistance to those in need. Local organizations, religious institutions, and volunteer groups can play a crucial role in offering solidarity, empathy, and tangible support to individuals grappling with economic hardships. Community-based initiatives can also help combat social isolation and provide a sense of belonging.

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